

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Widespread beta defensin genomic methylation in HER2+ breast cancer.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We studied epigenetic modification status across the genome in humans with breast cancer using whole genome SNP array. We identified beta defensin genomic methylation in HER2+ breast cancer in the primary tumor. We suggest methylation of beta defensin genes is a tumor silencing mechanism that targets a bactericidal function (defensin expression) that functions in early tumor development as an innate anti- tumor defense response.